

BEAM ON ELASTIC FOUNDATION AND MICO-FIBER BENDING

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SUMMARY: Micro-fiber reinforced cementitious composites are nowadays commonly used materials. It has been recognised that the quality of such material greatly depends on the behavior of fiber-matrix interaction. Fiber bending is one of the micro-mechanisms. While the partly debonded steel fiber is subjected to pulling force against the matrix and simultaneously transverse force, it may be modelled as a Bernoulli-Euler beam partly supported on a non-linear elastic foundation with variable modulus. In this paper, some typical models and the difficulties in solution procedures are reviewed. The governing equation of fiber bending on variable modulus foundation is proposed. Due to the inclusion of second order effect resulting from the transverse deflection, this model appears to be complex in the sense of solution process. Hence, reliable numerical techniques, such as Runge-Kutta method, multi-dimensional optimization approach, are introduced to form an out-layer loop for the solution. In the internal loop, numerical integration and analytical integration are applied. Since the out-layer loop is multi-dimensional and no tool can be said universal, the effectiveness of the proposed algorithm has been carefully examined. The influence of discrete intervals on the numerical integration is also investigated and the best interval number is found. The proposed solution strategy avoids some of the complexities of other proposals [1] and may be of use to both engineers and researchers.

KEYWORDS: Fiber bending, variable modulus foundation, second order effect, differential equation, optimization.

INTRODUCTION

In our study on micro-fiber reinforced cementitious composites, the micro-mechanism of fiber bending on elastic foundation is encountered and found that it may be treated as the classical beam bending problem. This problem, at the first glance, may be regarded as a simple issue. However, it could be very complex as it is commonly found in rail ways, roads, mechanical device, and bio-structures, etc., in both static and dynamic cases. The analysis can be traced back to about one and a half centuries ago. It is found that some models are comprehensive but turn out to be difficult to solve. In regard to solution method, analytical techniques are only suitable for some simple circumstances. Thus various discrete methods have been tried by investigators. If boundary conditions are relatively simple, the equation system is closed, that is, the problem is solvable even though else conditions may be complex. In our problem, since the second order effect of transverse deflection has to be included, the equation system is explicitly unclosed. It is not an ordinary boundary value problem. Therefore, an optimization technique is introduced to form an out-layer loop. In internal loops, conventional numerical and analytical integrations remain wherever applicable. Since the out-layer loop is multi-dimensional and no tool can be said universal, the effectiveness of the proposed algorithm should be carefully examined. This is done in the further study and will be reported in another paper. The influence of discrete intervals on the numerical integration is also instigated and the best interval number is found. This is reported in this article. The following will survey the major existing models on the beam on foundation problem and present the model for our problem and the corresponding solution strategy.

REVIEW OF MODELS FOR BEAM ON ELASTIC FOUNDATION PROBLEM

As early as in 1867, Winkler proposed a well-known model for an elastic foundation:

$$q(x, y) = k \cdot w(x, y) \quad (1)$$

where q is foundation response, k is the modulus, and w the deflection of the foundation. However, this model is considered as a crude approximation of the true mechanical behavior of various foundation materials. This situation gives rise to the construction of more general plate/beam-foundation interaction theories which may be roughly classified into two categories, according to Selvadurai [2], elastic continuum models and Winkler-type models. The former is regarded as mathematically complex, though this may be no longer a problem with up-to-date numerical algorithms and computers. The later have concise mathematical format which has particular attraction in dealing with one dimensional beam-foundation problem. The two-parameter elastic models are the representatives of the second category and the development may be attributed to the authors: Filonenko-Borodich [3],[4], Pasternak [5], Kerr [6], Vlazov and Leontiev [7], and so forth. This type of model may be written as the following form:

$$p(x, y) = kw(x, y) - k_1 \nabla^2 w(x, y) \quad (2)$$

where ∇ is the Laplace operator, k is the modulus of the elastic subgrade; k_1 is the second constant, which may be the tension coefficient according to Filonenko-Borodich model [3], [4] or, shear effectiveness according to Pasternak model [5] or, load-spreading effectiveness according to Vlazov [8] and Vlazov and Leontiev [7] models. It is noted that the Vlazov and Leontiev [7] model and Reissner [9] model take the foundation depth H into consideration, e.g. $k = E / H$.

Recently, non-linear elastic foundation, in analogy to the above two-parameter model has been proposed. For instance, third order nonlinear model [10],

$$p(x, y) = kw(x, y) - k_1 w^3(x, y) \quad (3)$$

fourth order nonlinear formulation [11],

$$p(x, y) = kw(x, y) - k_1 w^3(x, y) + k_1 w^4(x, y) \quad (4)$$

hyperbolic sine-type [12],

$$p = \frac{k}{n} \sinh(nw) \quad (5)$$

and hyperbolic type [1],

$$k = \frac{k_0}{1 + mw} \quad (6)$$

It is noted that a third approach to model the foundation response has also been proposed by some authors. In this category, formal power series expansions are performed in order to capture various deformational components in foundation or both deformation properties in the foundation and mechanical components in pressure response. The first sub-category proposed by Ratzersdorfer, Favre, and Levinson-Bharatha (all of which are quoted by Kerr [13]) may be expressed:

$$p = Lw \quad (7)$$

where L is a linear differential operator containing even order derivatives only.

The second sub-category is proposed by Kerr and Rhines (quoted by Kerr [13]) is expressed as:

$$Lp = Lw \quad (8)$$

Kerr [13] provided the expansion with physical explanations which indicate that a general foundation includes spring, shearing, and bending effect as well as their combinations.

It is also noted that Kerr and Rhines [13] model includes the parameter of foundation depth H as done in Vlazov and Leontiev [7] model and Reissner [9] model, though it is taken as a constant so is the spring coefficient k as a constant in turn.

The other treatment to elastic foundation is proposed by Vallabhan and Das [14]. They used two displacement functions to obtain matrix foundation response.

As mentioned above, some models already account for the foundation depth H in the spring constant k . This implies that k may not be a constant with respect to the position (x, y) if H varies with the coordinate. As the matter of fact, Hetenyi [15] has analysed the beam on the foundation with linearly varying modulus:

$$\frac{d^4 y(\mathbf{x})}{d\mathbf{x}^4} + \mathbf{a}\mathbf{x} \cdot y(\mathbf{x}) = 0 \quad (9)$$

However, this consideration may result in essential change in solution method since it alters the characteristic of the differential equation. Direct analytic solution for this high order differential equation seems not realistic. Therefore, Hetenyi proposed the following solution procedure which is composed of four infinite polynomial series:

$$y(\mathbf{x}) = c_1 y_1(\mathbf{x}) + c_2 y_2(\mathbf{x}) + c_3 y_3(\mathbf{x}) + c_4 y_4(\mathbf{x}) \quad (10)$$

where

$$y_1(\mathbf{x}) = 1 - \frac{\mathbf{a}}{5!} \mathbf{x}^5 + \frac{6\mathbf{a}^2}{10!} \mathbf{x}^{10} - \frac{6 \cdot 11\mathbf{a}^3}{15!} \mathbf{x}^{15} + \frac{6 \cdot 11 \cdot 16\mathbf{a}^4}{20!} \mathbf{x}^{20} - \dots$$

$$y_2(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{x} - \frac{2\mathbf{a}}{6!} \mathbf{x}^6 + \frac{2 \cdot 7\mathbf{a}^2}{11!} \mathbf{x}^{11} - \frac{2 \cdot 7 \cdot 12\mathbf{a}^3}{16!} \mathbf{x}^{16} + \frac{2 \cdot 7 \cdot 12 \cdot 17\mathbf{a}^4}{21!} \mathbf{x}^{21} - \dots$$

$$y_3(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{2!} \mathbf{x}^2 - \frac{3\mathbf{a}}{7!} \mathbf{x}^7 + \frac{3 \cdot 8\mathbf{a}^2}{12!} \mathbf{x}^{12} - \frac{3 \cdot 8 \cdot 13\mathbf{a}^3}{17!} \mathbf{x}^{17} + \frac{3 \cdot 8 \cdot 13 \cdot 18\mathbf{a}^4}{22!} \mathbf{x}^{22} - \dots$$

$$y_4(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{3!} \mathbf{x}^3 - \frac{4\mathbf{a}}{8!} \mathbf{x}^8 + \frac{4 \cdot 9\mathbf{a}^2}{13!} \mathbf{x}^{13} - \frac{4 \cdot 9 \cdot 14\mathbf{a}^3}{18!} \mathbf{x}^{18} + \frac{4 \cdot 9 \cdot 14 \cdot 19\mathbf{a}^4}{23!} \mathbf{x}^{23} - \dots$$

the coefficients $c_1 - c_4$ are unknown to be determined with boundary conditions.

The application of this theory has been performed by Liou and Lai [16]. According to their analysis, the accuracy of the truncation on the infinite series above depends on the value of \mathbf{a} , which should be limited within 10,000 for using the above series by truncating the terms after the fifth.

This problem, of course, can also be solved with numerical methods, for instance, finite difference technique [17], [18], B-spline technique [19], differential quadrature element method (DQEM) [20], and finite element method [21], [22], [23], [24], [25], [26]. However, for non-linear function, the finite difference method may encounter practical difficulty. For instance the convergence may not be guaranteed.

For a beam with varying cross section on an elastic foundation with constant modulus, we have another differential equation:

$$EI(x) \frac{d^4 y(x)}{dx^4} + k \cdot y(x) = 0 \quad (11)$$

where E is elastic beam modulus and $I(x)$ its area moment of inertia of the cross section at x . Again, it still a simple but good choice to use the numerical methods mentioned above. It is worth mention that many investigators resort to finite element method to solve this sort or even more complex issues, such as beam buckling, vibration, etc. [22], [23], [24], [25], [27]. However, for static single beam problem, one may tend to chose compact and easy-to-use methods.

It is noticed that, for most of the problems in literature, the corresponding boundaries at one end or both form a closed solution system so that no essential difficulty exists no matter which solving technique is selected.

This study deals with a cantilever partly supported on an elastic foundation with varying modulus (Fig. 1). To simplify the model, one-parameter non-linear modulus expression is selected. The second order geometric effect is included. Thus the equation system is not directly closed for the solution. In order to simplify the solution procedure, transformation of higher order differential equation into one order simultaneous differential equations is performed and Runge-Kutta method is utilised for the solution of the beam on the foundation with non-linear modulus. For the cantilever part (Fig. 1), analytic formula is remained. To deal with the un-closed boundaries, two dimensional optimization technique is employed. The numerical process displays stable convergence.

MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF BEAM ON FOUNDATION WITH NON-LINEAR MODULUS

While dealing with a steel fiber lying on an elastic foundation with varying thickness, we found it may be more proper to express the foundation stiffness with a non-linear function than other ways, according to the finite element analysis result provided by Leung and Li [27]. Thus the elastic foundation stiffness (Fig. 1) is proposed to be:

$$k(x) = C_a \cdot [C_b (l_b - \Delta - x) \cdot \frac{2}{D_f \tan(\mathbf{j})}]^r \quad (12)$$

where C_a , C_b , r , and Δ are constants, D_f and \mathbf{j} are diameter and the inclined angle of fiber, respectively.

Fig. 1. Analysis of fiber bending

In expectation of mathematical difficulty, the general fourth order beam equation is not used here. Instead, we simply account for the moment at x . The advantage of this manipulation is that the higher order of foundation reaction will not be lost. Hence the deflection curve of the fiber loaded as in Fig. 1 can be described by the following differential equation [28]:

$$EI \frac{d^2 y}{dx^2} = F_B (l_b - x) - F_T (y_b - y) - H(l_c - x) \cdot \int_x^{l_c} k(t)y(t)dt \quad (13)$$

where E and I are the modulus of elasticity and the moment of inertia of the fiber respectively, $k(x)$ is the elastic stiffness of the foundation, and $H(t)$ is Herath's function:

$$H(l_c - x) = \begin{cases} 0, & l_c - x < 0 \\ 1, & l_c - x > 0 \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

While $x > l_c$, equation (13) has a general solution:

$$y = c_1 e^{px} + c_2 e^{-px} + y_b - \frac{F_B}{F_T} (l_b - x) \quad (15)$$

where $p^2 = F_T / EI$. Substituting left boundary conditions into eq. (15) yields:

$$c_1 = \frac{e^{-pl_c}}{2} [-y_b + y_c + \frac{y'_c}{p} + I_2] \quad (a)$$

$$\text{and } c_2 = \frac{e^{pl_c}}{2} [-y_b + y_c - \frac{y'_c}{p} + I_3] \quad (b)$$

where $I_1 = \frac{F_B}{F_T} (l_b - l_c)$, $I_2 = I_1 - \frac{F_B}{pF_T}$, and $I_3 = I_1 + \frac{F_B}{pF_T}$. Substituting eq. (a) and (b) into eq. (15) gives:

$$y_b = y_c + \frac{y'_c}{p} \operatorname{tgh} a + \frac{1}{2 \cosh a} (I_2 e^a + I_3 e^{-a}) \quad (16)$$

where $a = p(l_b - l_c)$.

By back-substituting (16) into (a) and (b), and finally into (15), we obtain the solution of deflection of the fiber, provided that the value of y_c and y'_c are known.

NUMERICAL STRATEGIES

While $x < l_c$, equation (13) gives the following form:

$$EI \frac{d^2 y}{dx^2} = F_B \cdot (l_b - x) - F_T \cdot (y_b - y) + \int_c^x k(t) \cdot y(t) \cdot t dt \quad (17)$$

Differentiating eq. (17) gives:

$$EI \frac{d^3 y}{dx^3} = -F_B + F_T \frac{dy}{dx} + k(x) \cdot xy \quad (18)$$

Formula (18) is a high order differential equation with a variable function $k(x)$. It is difficult to find analytic solution for this differential equation. Though this equation may be solved with series solutions, it is complex to assess the truncation errors and so to manipulate the inner boundary conditions at location c (Fig. 1). We shall, therefore, explore numerical methods for the solution.

Let $d_1 = -\frac{F_B}{EI}$, $d_2 = \frac{1}{EI}$, $d_3 = \frac{F_T}{EI}$, eq. (18) becomes:

$$y''' = d_1 + d_2 k(x) xy + d_3 y' \quad (19)$$

Let us perform the following transformation:

$$Y_1 = y, Y_2 = Y_1' = y', Y_3 = Y_2' = y'', \text{ and} \\ Y_1' = y' = Y_2, Y_2' = y'' = Y_3, Y_3' = y''' = d_1 + d_2 k(x) \cdot x Y_1 + d_3 Y_2, \text{ or}$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} Y_1 \\ Y_2 \\ Y_3 \end{pmatrix}' = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ d_2 x k(x) & d_3 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} Y_1 \\ Y_2 \\ Y_3 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ d_1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (20)$$

This formula is a standard first order differential equation group and can be solved with numerical method. In the following, the fourth order Runge-Kutta method will be employed.

The boundary conditions for eq. (20) are given as (Fig. 1):

$$Y_1|_{x=0} = y|_{x=0} = 0 \\ Y_2|_{x=0} = y'|_{x=0} = 0$$

$$Y_3 \Big|_{x=0} = y'' \Big|_{x=0} = [F_B l_b - F_T y_b - \int_0^c k(x)y(x)xdx] / EI \quad (21)$$

$$Y_1 \Big|_{x=l_c} = y \Big|_{x=l_c} = y_c$$

$$Y_2 \Big|_{x=l_c} = y' \Big|_{x=l_c} = y'_c$$

$$Y_3 \Big|_{x=l_c} = y'' \Big|_{x=l_c} = [F_B (l_b - l_c) - F_T (y_b - y_c)] / EI$$

The boundary condition at $x = l_c$ indicates that the numerical solution at position c (Fig. 1) gives the initial values to the equation (16) and (15), and hence the whole solution for the beam. However, it is shown that the initial boundary (at $x = 0$) contains the undetermined function $y(x)$ and the end displacement y_b . Therefore further solution method should be introduced.

Let the exact solution be $\bar{u} = \int_0^c k(x)y(x)xdx$ and $\bar{v} = y_b$. If trial value u_i and v_i infinitely approach \bar{u} and \bar{v} , i.e., $\lim(u_i - \bar{u}) \Rightarrow 0$, and $\lim(v_i - \bar{v}) \Rightarrow 0$, certain values of them within an expected small deviation can be accepted as the solution after finite iterations. For this situation, we may construct a function such as:

$$f(u, v) = [(w_1 |u - \bar{u}|)^a + (w_2 |v - \bar{v}|)^b]^{2/a+b} \quad (22)$$

where w_1 and w_2 are weights, a and b are constants. If $w_1 = w_2 = 1$ and $a = b = 2$, $f(u, v)$ is distance between (u, v) and (\bar{u}, \bar{v}) . The above problem is now transformed into a task of root finding, i. e., finding a solution $(u^*, v^*) \Rightarrow (\bar{u}, \bar{v})$ so that $f(u^*, v^*) \Rightarrow 0$. As (\bar{u}, \bar{v}) are unknowns, some sort of iteration method must be employed. However equation (22) is a 2-dimensional problem, so the initial guess, which is crucial to the problem, will be difficult to determine and thus convergence or expected result may not be guaranteed with the available numerical techniques [29]. Secondly, since (u, v) and (\bar{u}, \bar{v}) are associated by the complex implicit function described above, function derivative are not available for the solution procedure. Hence all solving strategies relying on the features of continuous function are not accounted in the current attempt.

Observing equation (22), the purpose to solve it is to find a very good proximate combination of (\bar{u}, \bar{v}) , or in other words, to find an effective strategy to generate a sequence of $(\bar{u}_i, \bar{v}_i), i = 1, 2, \dots, n$ so that their difference from the output (u, v) approach zero. It is clear that the function value will not be equal to zero unless $\bar{u} = u$ and $\bar{v} = v$. In fact, this function can be treated as minimization problem with extremum as zero. Optimization techniques may provide some attractive strategies to generate sequences of $(\bar{u}_i, \bar{v}_i), i = 1, 2, \dots, n$. Since the concerned problem is two-dimensional, non-linear and non-differentiable, we chose Downhill Simplex Method (DSM) in multi-dimensions (Press, et al. 1989) for the solution.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

Downhill Simplex Method (DSM) in multi-dimensions is due to Nelder and Mead (1965). It is function evaluations dependent only. The function derivative is not necessary. It might not be fast comparing with other techniques, e.g., Powell's method, but may be robust and convenient. It is found that the computing time is not a major concern while using the high performance computer system at the University of Queensland. The principal steps of this method include formation of initial simplex, reflection, expansion, rebounding, and contraction. However, there is not a universal optimization tool that guarantees the global

extremities being found. Therefore, it is suggested (Press, et al., [29] 1989) to restart a multidimensional minimization routine at a point where it claims to have found a minimum. In this study, we use a random number generator, which was provided by Dr. Jim Brown of the University of Dundee, UK, to produce initial points for DSM in the search domain. For each re-run, we still randomly select the re-starting points except the best point of the last run.

By re-writing equation (22) as a distance between inputs and outputs and minimise it, we have:

$$\min f(\bar{u}, \bar{v}) = \{[w_1(u - \bar{u})]^2 + [w_2(v - \bar{v})]^2\}^{1/2} \quad (23)$$

In this study, the weights are substituted with $w_1 = 1/u$, $w_2 = 1/v$. For the example computation, the parameters of the above fiber bending model are initiated as: $l_b = 15$ mm, $l_c = 7$ mm, $F_t = 2.5$ N, $F_b = 4.33$ N (Fig. 1), elastic modulus of the foundation matrix $E_m = 30$ GPa, elastic modulus of fiber $E_f = 210$ GPa, the diameter of fiber $D_f = 0.5$ mm. For the sake of demonstration of the algorithm, it is assumed that both fiber and matrix remain elastic under the supposed load. After lengthy test on DSM code, the search domain has been focused on $u \in (0, 65)$ versus $v \in (0, 1.5)$. In this study, much attention has been paid on the effectiveness of the Runge-Kutta integration and the optimization technique. The latter will be reported in another paper. For the numerical integration, the discrete interval has significant impact on the integration precision. This influence is shown in Table 1. It is displayed that while the interval is 120, the minimal deviation is $-1.106090\text{E-}06$ and $2.135360\text{E-}04$ for u and v , respectively. And the corresponding solution is $u = 6.055140\text{E+}01$ (N.mm) and $v = 1.100910\text{E+}00$ (mm).

Table. 1 Influence of integration intervals

Intervals	U	V	du/u	Dv/v
10	5.952780E+01	1.499790E+00	-3.229260E-02	1.569580E+00
30	6.059820E+01	1.081920E+00	3.453040E-04	1.514620E-03
60	6.057840E+01	1.090090E+00	2.117620E-04	-2.195810E-03
90	6.056440E+01	1.095690E+00	-1.755340E-04	-1.912610E-03
120	6.055140E+01	1.100910E+00	-1.106090E-06	2.135360E-04
150	6.054840E+01	1.102090E+00	5.314780E-04	-3.431500E-04

The results of the above computation can also be verified with an approximate analytic calculation. Since in this example, the deflection at end B (Fig. 1) is dominated by the cantilever section, namely, section CB . Let $y_c = 0$ and $y'_c = 0$, which assume section CB as a cantilever with rigid anchorage, eq. (16) becomes:

$$y_b = \frac{1}{2 \cosh \mathbf{a}} (\mathbf{I}_2 e^{\mathbf{a}} + \mathbf{I}_3 e^{-\mathbf{a}}) \quad (24)$$

where $p = \sqrt{F_T/EI} = 0.0622924$, $\mathbf{a} = p(l_b - l_c) = 0.498339$, $\mathbf{I}_1 = (l_b - l_c)F_B / F_T = 13.856$, $\mathbf{I}_2 = \mathbf{I}_1 - F_B / (p * F_T) = -13.948355$, $\mathbf{I}_3 = \mathbf{I}_1 + F_B / (p * F_T) = 41.660355$, hence:

$$y_b = \frac{1}{2 \cosh(0.498339)} (-13.948355 e^{0.498339} + 41.660355 e^{-0.498339}) = 1.043479 \text{ mm}$$

This value is slightly smaller than the corresponding value (1.100910 mm) of the original structure (Fig. 1), which means the above computed results are reasonable.

CONCLUSIONS

To improve the fiber reinforced composites, we have to understand the micro-mechanisms of fiber-matrix interactions. Fiber bending is one of the mechanisms and is investigated in this study. As it is realised that fiber bending may be treated as classical beam on elastic foundation problem, surveying on the corresponding models has been carried out. It is found that some models are very complex and special treatment or techniques are needed for the solution, in particular, for the non-linear foundations. However, the authors' problem faces second order effect resulting from transverse deflection. This effect leads to unclosed equation system. Thus out-layer iteration loop is introduced. The Downhill Simplex Method (DSM) is employed as the iteration strategy. The selection of the iteration strategies and convergence of DSM have been carefully studied and will be reported in another article. For computation of deflection, some well known discretization numerical methods, e.g., FEM or difference method, are not used. Instead, Runge-Kutta method is applied to simplify the solution procedure. To verify the effectiveness of the numerical integration, numerical test has been performed and the best discretization size has been found. The final result shows satisfactory precision. In regard to the extensive application background of this problem, it is hoped that the proposed method might be beneficial to engineers and investigators in various fields who are likely encountering similar problems but attempt to avoid being entangled in sophisticated mathematical issues, such as the treatment reported in [1].

REFERENCES

1. Soldatos, K. P., and Selvadurai, A. P. S., "Flexure of beams on hyperbolic elastic foundation", *Int. J. Solids Struct.*, 1985. Vol. 21, No. 4
2. Selvadurai, A. P. S., *Elastic analysis of soil-foundation interaction*, Elsevier sci. Publishing Co., 1979.
3. Filonenko-Borodich, M. M., Some approximate theories of the elastic foundation, *Uch. Zap. Mosk. Gos. Univ. Mekh.*, 1940, Vol. 46 (in Russia)
4. Filonenko-Borodich, M. M., "A very simple model of an elastic foundation capable of spreading the load", *Sb. Tr. Mosk. Elektro. Inst. Inzh. Trans.*, 1945. No: 53, Transzheldorizdat (in Russian).
5. Pasternak, P. L., "On a new method of analysis of an elastic foundation by means of two foundation constants", 1954, *Gos. Izd. Lit. po Strait I Arkh*, Moscow, the Soviet Union (in Russia)
6. Kerr, A. D., "Elastic and viscoelastic foundation models", *J. Appl. Mech.*, 1964. Vol. 31.
7. Vlasov, V. Z., and Leont'ev, N. N., *Beams, plates and shells on elastic foundations*, Israel Program for Scientific Translations, Jerusalem, Israel, 1966.
8. Vlasov, V. Z., *General theory of shells and its application in engineering*, Gosterkhizdat, Moscow, Leningrad (in Russia), 1949.
9. Reissner, E., "A note on deflections of plates on a viscoelastic foundation", *ASME, J. Appl. Mech.*, 1958. Vol. 25.
10. Waas, A. M., "Initial postbuckling behavior of beams on non-linear elastic foundations", *Mech. Res. Commun.*, 1990. Vol. 17, No. 4.
11. Huk, D., "Postbuckling behavior of infinite beams on elastic foundations using Koiter's improved theory", *Int. J. Non-linear Mech.*, 1988. Vol. 23, No. 2.
12. Kerr, A. D., "Buckling of continuously supported beams", *ASCE, J. Eng. Mech. Div.*, 1969. Vol. 95, No. EM1.
13. Kerr, A. D., "On the formal development of elastic foundation models", *Ing.-Arc.*, 1984. Vol. 54.
14. Vallabhan, C. V. G., and Das, Y. C., "Improved model for beams on elastic foundations", *Elastic-Plastic Failure Modelling of Structures with Applications* Presented at the 1988

- ASME Pressure Vessels and Piping Conference. Pittsburgh, PA, USA, v 141. Publ by ASME, New York, NY, USA.
15. Hetenyi, M., *Beams on elastic foundation*, University of Michigan Press, Ann Arbor, Mich., 1946.
 16. Liu, G.-S., and Lai, S. C., “Structural analysis model for mat foundations”, ASCE, *J. Struct. Eng.*, 1996. Vol. 122, No. 9.
 17. Lentini, M., “Numerical solution of the beam equation with nonuniform foundation coefficient”, *J. Appl. Mech.*, 1979. Vol. 46.
 18. Vallabhan, C. V. G., and Das, Y. C., “Modified Vlasov model for beams on elastic foundations”, ASCE, *J. Geo. Eng.*, 1991. Vol. 117, No. 6.
 19. Bechtold, J. E., and Riley, D. R., “Application of beams on elastic foundation and B-spline solution methodologies to parametric analysis of intramedullary implant systems”, *J. Biomech.*, 1991. Vol. 24, No. 6.
 20. Chen, C. N., “Solution of beam on elastic foundation by DQEM”, ASCE, *J. Eng. Mech.*, 1998. Vol. 124, No. 12.
 21. Ting, B. Y., and Mockry, E. F., “Beam on elastic foundation finite element”, ASCE, *J. Struct. Eng.*, 1984. Vol. 110.
 22. Mourelatos, Z. P., and Parsons, M. G., “Finite element analysis of beams on elastic foundation including shear and axial effects”, *Compt. Struct.*, 1987. Vol. 27, No. 3.
 23. Leung, C. K. Y. and Chi, J., “Crack-bridging force in random ductile fiber brittle matrix composites”, ASCE *J. Enq. Mech.*, 1995. Vol. 121, No. 12.
 24. Wasti, S. T., and Senkaya, E., “Simple finite element for beams on elastic foundations”, *Strain*, 1995. Vol. 31, No. 4.
 25. Thambiratnam, D. and Zhuge, Y., “Free vibration analysis of beams on elastic foundation”, *Compt. Struct.*, 1996. Vol. 60, No. 6.
 26. Al-Nageim, H., Mohammed, F., and Lesley, L., “Numerical results of the LR55 track system modelled as multilayer beams on elastic foundation”, *J. Construct. Steel Res.*, 1998. Vol. 46, No. 1-3.
 27. Leung, C. K. Y., and Li, V. C., “Effect of fiber inclination on crack bridging stress in brittle fiber reinforced brittle matrix composites”, *J. Mech. Phys. Solids*, 1992. Vol. 40, No. 6.
 28. Timoshenko, S., *Strength of materials, Part II*, 3rd ed., D. Van Nostrand Company, Inc., 1956.
 29. Press, W. H., Flannery, B. P., Teukolsky, S. A., and Vetterling, W. T., *Numerical recipes*, Cambridge University Press, 1989, pp. 289-293.